

Toward a generalizable framework for robot-aided percutaneous surgery

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Abstract—Robot-aided percutaneous surgery faces significant challenges due to organ deformation between preoperative and intraoperative phases. This work presents an integrated framework including: deformable registration algorithm for aligning pre/intraoperative 3D models; real-time motion planner for needle path replanning; advanced teleoperated control strategy for needle insertion. The registration algorithm achieved an RMSE of 1.7 ± 0.5 mm with real-time suitability on clinical datasets. Validation of the planning and control modules on a phantom model with non-expert users showed improved needle orientation and positioning accuracy (maximum deviation: 0.006 ± 0.003 rad, target error: 0.8 ± 0.9 mm). Clinical experts confirmed system feasibility with moderate cognitive workload.

Index Terms—Percutaneous surgery, Surgical robotics, Image registration, Intraoperative planning, Teleoperated control

I. INTRODUCTION

Minimally Invasive Percutaneous Surgery (MIPS) enables access to deep anatomical structures through needle puncture, offering reduced patient trauma and improved outcomes compared to open approaches. However, intraoperative anatomical changes such as organ shifts, deformations, and positioning variations commonly compromise pre-planned needle paths. This limitation is particularly evident in procedures like percutaneous nephrolithotomy, where kidney displacement between supine preoperative imaging and prone intraoperative positioning significantly impacts the access route [1].

To address these challenges, several registration algorithms have been proposed to achieve accurate preoperative-to-intraoperative alignment. Among these, geometric registration methods offer the optimal trade-off between accuracy and computational efficiency, enabling real-time alignment of preoperative 3D models with intraoperative data [2]. Once alignment is achieved, intraoperative replanning becomes essential to adapt needle trajectories based on updated anatomical information while maintaining patient safety. Teleoperated robotic systems represent a promising solution, as they preserve direct surgeon control while ensuring safe workspace constraints, avoiding the risks of autonomous systems in unmodeled scenarios and the radiation exposure inherent to cooperative approaches.

However, existing teleoperated robotic systems for percutaneous procedures focus on needle insertion without consid-

ering preoperative-to-intraoperative alignment and real-time replanning capabilities [3]. This limitation represents a significant gap in current robot-aided percutaneous surgery frameworks.

Therefore, this study introduces an *integrated framework for robot-aided percutaneous surgery* that combines pre-to-intraoperative deformable registration with a novel motion planner for intraoperative trajectory replanning and a teleoperated control strategy for needle insertion, enabling surgeons to adapt to intraoperative anatomical changes while maintaining precise trajectory control. The framework is designed to operate *independently* of specific robotic platforms or procedure types, thereby supporting broad integration across surgical systems and percutaneous interventions.

II. THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

The proposed framework workflow is illustrated in Fig. 1a. Following 3D anatomical model reconstruction from medical imaging, a deformable registration algorithm aligns preoperative and intraoperative models to compensate for organ deformations and enable AR-based surgical guidance. Then, through teleoperation, a motion planner enables the surgeon to replan the trajectory of the needle connected to the robot based on the registered anatomy, followed by needle insertion.

A. Deformable registration algorithm

After 3D reconstruction from preoperative and intraoperative imaging using standard techniques from the literature [4], for example visual Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) or deep learning-based approaches, deformable registration is performed through *Coherent Point Drift combined with Optimized Volumetric Deformation* (CPD+OpVD). Point clouds are extracted from both models, and a projection-based partial selection identifies the portion of the preoperative model consistent with the intraoperative field of view. CPD estimates a non-rigid transformation through probabilistic correspondence matching, while OpVD propagates the deformation to the full preoperative model, producing a point cloud that accurately reflects intraoperative anatomy.

B. Real-time motion planner

Once intraoperative feedback is available through AR, the surgeon can replan the needle trajectory if required. During this phase, it is essential to preserve a safety margin from the patient's skin and maintain the needle oriented toward the anatomical target. This is achieved through a novel motion planner based on a combination of a *cylindrical motion planner* and an *orientation planner*. The cylindrical planner maps haptic interface inputs along the x_m and z_m axes

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Fig. 1. a) Workflow of the proposed framework for robot-aided percutaneous surgery, b) advanced teleoperated control strategy for needle insertion.

into an angular displacement θ along the cylindrical surface and an axial displacement Δz (see Fig. 1a), constraining needle motion to a virtual cylinder. The orientation planner ensures that the needle axis remains aligned with the vector connecting the needle origin to the target at each instant through appropriate rotation matrices. During this phase, the haptic interface is governed by PD control, enforcing rigid interaction along the y_m axis, while the robot operates under conventional position control in the operational space.

C. Teleoperated control architecture

At this stage, the surgeon proceeds with needle insertion using a novel combined control strategy based on inverse dynamics control. The haptic interface is governed by a PD control law, which in this case enforces rigid interaction along the x_m and z_m axes. The robot control architecture integrates a *parallel position/velocity mode* (S1) with a *master-slave position error-based mode* (S2), as illustrated in Fig. 1b. In S1, velocity control is applied along the insertion axis y_s , while position control constrains x_s and z_s motions to provide surgeon guidance; in S2, all three axes are controlled in position with maintained constraints on x_s and z_s . This combined approach was adopted since velocity control provides smoother motion, suitable for the initial insertion tract, whereas position control offers higher accuracy, making it preferable for target approach and final depth adjustment.

The stabilizing action of the proposed control is expressed as:

$$y = J_A^\dagger(q) [Ad^{-1} (K_P Ad\tilde{x} - K_D Ad\dot{\tilde{x}} + K_F F_R)] \quad (1)$$

where J_A^\dagger is the right pseudo-inverse of the analytical Jacobian, Ad is the adjoint matrix mapping the pose error \tilde{x} to the end-effector frame, and K_P and K_D are the position control gains. The force term $K_F F_R$ is present only in S1, with F_R proportional to the velocity tracking error. The stabilizing action results in linear second-order error dynamics, which guarantee asymptotic stability under positive-definite gains and a nonsingular Jacobian.

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The **registration algorithm** was validated on two public liver datasets: i) DePoLL, comprising a porcine preoperative 3D model and 13 intraoperative deformed models, and ii) OpenCAS, including three simulated tests with preoperative and deformed intraoperative models and a phantom acquisition. An internal dataset from robot-assisted partial nephrectomy procedures was also used, with data from three patients including preoperative 3D kidney models and corresponding

Fig. 2. a) Experimental setup, b) CPD+OpVD deformation example.

intraoperative reconstructions. Performance, assessed in terms of *execution time* and *RMSE reduction* relative to rigid registration, achieved median values of 15 s [IQR: 6.5–38.5] and 72.95% [IQR: 63.4–82.5], respectively, confirming accuracy and real-time suitability for surgical workflows since the registration is performed once at the beginning of the operation (qualitative example shown in Fig. 2b). The **planning and control modules** were validated using the setup in Fig. 2a. Six non-expert users performed needle replanning and insertion in a percutaneous nephrolithotomy scenario on a gelatin-based anatomical phantom, under direct visual feedback. Evaluation metrics included *orientation deviation* from replanned trajectory, *target positioning error* (Euclidean distance between target and needle tip), and *motion smoothness* (mean/max velocity ratio). Results demonstrated maximum deviation of 0.006 ± 0.003 rad, smoothness of 0.13 ± 0.08 , and target error of 0.8 ± 0.9 mm. Six clinical experts further assessed workload with NASA-TLX questionnaire, reporting a moderate average score of 58.2 ± 12.8 .

IV. CONCLUSION

This work presented an integrated framework that combines deformable registration, real-time replanning, and teleoperated needle insertion for robot-aided percutaneous surgery. Experimental validation demonstrated feasibility and robustness, while expert assessment confirmed its potential for clinical translation. Future work will address larger-scale studies and integration into surgical workflows.

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